

D7.2. Dissemination and Communication Plan

March 2025

Deliverable Information Sheet

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¹ **Type** [1] R=Document, report; DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; DEC=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER=other_

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Document verification and approval

	Name	Organisation	Date	Visa
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Project Coordinator	Carmen Fernández Ayuso	CETEC	01/03/2025	OK

List of Acronyms

PHAs	polyhydroxyalkanoates
D&C plan	Dissemination and Communication Plan
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators

Keywords list

Agricultural biotechnology, Industrial biotechnology, Materials engineering, Nanotechnology, Agrochemicals, Delivery systems, Agricultural plastics, Biopolymers, Polyhydroxyalkanoates, PHAs, Mulch film, Foam, Fertilizer, Pesticide, Circular economy.

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1. Executive summary

This document presents the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C plan) of the PHAntastic project.

The PHAntastic Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C plan) is the foundation on which the dissemination and exploitation of the project work, impacts and results are based on. It defines the overarching communication and dissemination strategy and the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to ensure that key PHAntastic stakeholders are engaged and activated in an appropriate and timely manner, and the project creates synergies with other initiatives for a greater impact.

The introduction describes the main aim of the document and its pursuit. The initial D&C plan is submitted in M7 and will be reviewed periodically with the active participation of all partners. This document is part of the activities carried out in WP7 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activities”, but it will actively follow the results and outputs from the other work packages.

Section 3 introduces a preliminary identification of key stakeholders supporting dissemination and communication activities including end users, research and academia, agrifood residues providers, public administration, regulatory entities, civil society, general public and tailored messages in order to put into place effective communication and dissemination campaigns to target all relevant and interested stakeholders.

Section 4, dissemination and communication activities and tools, presents the visual identity of the PHAntastic project, dissemination and communication materials and the communication and dissemination strategy for the project, explaining how partners will contribute to the dissemination process, ensuring that communication efforts are aligned and impactful.

Section 5 introduces key performance indicators for monitoring dissemination and communication activities and Section 6 procedures for communication, dissemination and privacy policy.

Section 7 summarizes how the D&C plan will address challenges and effectively communicate project outcomes based on the project’s objectives.

2. Introduction

The PHAntastic project uses polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) to develop biodegradable mulch film and growth foam delivery systems, reducing the need for synthetic agrochemical inputs and non-biodegradable polymers. The two families of PHA-based delivery systems containing active bioproducts are demonstrated in European horticultural and tree nursery settings (TRL 6). The project will contribute to the elimination of 23,000 tons of agrochemicals and 680 tons of microplastics by 2050.

Coordinated by CETEC, this €7.4M Horizon Europe initiative (2024–2028) supports sustainable agriculture and aligns with EU targets for reduced environmental impact and enhanced food security.

The D&C plan provides a clear overview on how all communication channels, activities, and tools work together to address and engage the relevant stakeholder groups (see Table 1) to achieve the dissemination objectives within WP7 to facilitate dialogue between farmers, scientists, policymakers, consumers, citizens and society while promoting the flow of knowledge on potential developments in agricultural biotechnology.

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, specific WP7 objectives are:

- To maximise public awareness and visibility among key stakeholders and end-users.
- To communicate to the general public the objectives and achievements of the project.

Encompassing all other work packages aside from Project Management (WP8), the successful deployment of the D&C plan involves the active contribution of all PHAntastic partners.

Figure 1. Work Plan structure.

The initial D&C plan is submitted in M7 and will be reviewed at intervals with the active participation of all partners. Revisions will accompany the report on dissemination and communication activities at D7.3 (M15), D7.4(M36) with the final D7.5, D7.6 and D7.7 reports on communication, dissemination and networking activities due in M48. Additionally, a close collaboration will be formed between the horizontal work packages (5,6,8) to ensure effective communication and dissemination of the project results.

The PHAntastic D&C plan includes the following elements:

- *Key stakeholders and targets of dissemination*
- *Dissemination and communication activities and tools:*
 - *Visual identity and communication templates*
 - *Communication actions*
 - *Dissemination actions*
- *KPIs /Monitoring of dissemination and communication activities*
- *Procedures and privacy policy*

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3. Key stakeholders and targets of dissemination

At the heart of the D&C plan are the PHAntastic stakeholders – those supporting the co-development of transition pathways and ensuring their realisation in policy, research and business areas. In the Grant Agreement, the consortium identified the following primary stakeholder groups:

Table 1. Target audience of the project

No.	Target audience ²	Focus	Objective to reach	Message
1	End-users of fertilizers, pesticides, and agricultural plastics (e.g., horticultural producers, tree nurseries)	D, C, E	To make them aware of the advantages of PHAntastic delivery systems and ease their role as future customers.	Performance, economic and environmental benefits of employing PHAntastic delivery systems
2	Producers of agri-food residues (e.g., growers, farmers)	D, C, E	To inform them of the applications of agri-food residues and establish rapport with possible future providers of feedstock	Economic and corporate benefits of agri-food residues management with PHAntastic
3	Research and academia	D, C	To provide the R&D community with new knowledge related to bio-based and biodegradable materials, as well as active bioproducts for agricultural purposes and PHAntastic effect on the soil microbial biodiversity.	Avant-garde advancements in production of bio-based and biodegradable polymers and their combination with plant and soil beneficial active bioproducts
4	Regulatory entities and public administration (policy makers, national and regional public authorities)	D, C	To spark discussion about policy and regulatory actions to boost alternative bio-based and biodegradable alternatives to agricultural plastics and traditional	Barriers and opportunities for alternative bio-based and biodegradable polymers and substitutes of traditional agrochemicals

² See examples below the table for each target audience.

			agrochemicals, in line with the goals of the EU.	
5	Other relevant European, national or regional initiatives, funding programs, clusters, and platforms	D, C	To create synergies, share knowledge and maximize the impact of the efforts.	Methodology, lessons learnt, D&C efforts
6	Civil society (e.g., environmental NGOs and consumer associations)	D, C	To improve project reach among stakeholders.	Project information, background and results
7	General public	C	To raise awareness and acceptance of bio-based and biodegradable polymers.	Importance of bio-based and biodegradable plastics, project info

Examples of target audience(s):

End-users of fertilizers, pesticides, and agricultural plastics: European Nurserystock Association (ENA), Copa-Cogeca, Dutch Greenhouse Horticulture (Glastuinbouw Nederland), Spanish Federation of Agricultural Producers (FEPEX), Italian Association of Agricultural Producers (Coldiretti), Swedish Farmers Federation (LRF), Belgian Federation of Horticulture (VLAM), Bulgarian National Association of Agricultural Producers (NSSAB).

Producers of agri-food residues: European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA), EU Organic Farmers Association (IFOAM EU), Italian Farmers Confederation (CIA), German Farmers' Association (DBV), Netherlands Agricultural Producers' Organisation (LTO Nederland), Spanish Agro-Food Cooperative (Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España), Swedish Farmers' Association (Lantbrukarnas Riksförbund - LRF), Belgian Federation of Agriculture (Boerenbond), Bulgarian National Association of Agricultural Producers (NSSAB).

Research and academia: Wageningen University & Research, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Ghent University, University of Barcelona (UB).

Regulatory entities and public administration: European Commission (DG SANTE, AGRI, ENV), European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Italian Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies, Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (Naturvårdsverket), Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature, and Food Quality (LNV), Belgian Ministry of Environment (Ministerie van Leefmilieu), Bulgarian Ministry of Agriculture and Food, Austrian Federal Ministry for Agriculture, Regions, and Tourism (BMLRT).

Other relevant European, national or regional initiatives, clusters and platforms: Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC), Circular Bio-based Europe (CBE JU), European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, Horizon Europe projects (e.g.,

Agro2Circular, REBIOLUTION), Dutch Bioplastics Alliance (NBA), Italian Bioplastics Consortium (CIB), Sweden's Green Chemistry Initiative, Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO), Austrian Bioeconomy Cluster (ABC), Bulgarian Bioplastics Association.

Civil society: Friends of the Earth Europe, European Environmental Bureau (EEB), Zero Waste Europe, BEUC (The European Consumer Organisation), Plastic Soup Foundation, Spanish Environmental Platform (Ecologistas en Acción), Italian Environmental League (Lega Ambiente), Swedish Society for Nature Conservation (SSNC), Flemish environmental group (Groen), Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation (BBF), Austrian Environmental Protection Agency (Umweltbundesamt).

General public: science communication initiatives (e.g., EU Green Week, EIT Food public engagement programs).

Not yet approved by the EC.

4. Dissemination and communication activities and tools

Visual identity and communication templates

The visual identity of the project will differentiate PHAntastic from other projects working on advanced biobased materials for sustainable agriculture. It comprises the logo, icon, and slogan. The logo will be the visual messenger of the project and will be reflected in all the communication materials:

Figure 2. PHAntastic logo.

The icon of the PHAntastic includes a cycloalkane, together with the PHAntastic wordmark. The cycloalkane represents the projects relevance to the use of biopolymers.

The slogan (also known as the tagline) is an actionable statement representing the goal of the project:

- *Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil*

An icon was created which can be used when there is a lack of space, or it is more optimal to represent the project:

Figure 3. PHAntastic icon.

The icon is utilised on social media platforms as account profile photos and other communication materials as needed. A comprehensive guide on the correct usage of the logo, tagline, and the project colour scheme can be found the Visual Guidelines.

D&C materials

The PHAntastic project will create a selection of communication materials, such as the leaflets/infographics, templates for deliverables, presentations and press releases, as well as roll-ups for in-person events and online banners and shareables for websites and social media. These materials are to be updated based on the project's needs and can be translated at partners' will into the other languages, as seemed necessary.

To harmonise the communications of the project and align efforts of all partners, REVOLVE will supply partners with a communication kit. The communication kit will include:

- *Visual Identity Guidelines- see page 27 & Logo Pack*
- *Templates (Word, Excel, PowerPoint, Press Release, roll-ups, poster) – see page 40-79*
- *Project Flyer/leaflet*
- *Other graphics/visuals as needed / requested by partners*

Based on the visual identity, templates for Microsoft Word and Microsoft PowerPoint have been developed. All partners have access to these assets for all communication and presentations about PHAntastic throughout the lifetime of the project.

The templates were developed accounting for any applicable rules and regulations from the European Commission. As with the other dimensions of this communication strategy, this Kit will be updated and revised more regularly with user-input from partners and in accordance with the deliverables that may emerge during the course of the project. As WP7 lead, REVOLVE is there to provide in-house support to all partners upon request for adapting the templates to their needs for example or with the formatting of reports and other knowledge products for PHAntastic. Additionally, 3 videos will be published, presenting the work done by the partners and emphasising key elements of the project.

Communication actions

This chapter outlines the comprehensive digital communication and dissemination strategy for the PHAntastic project. It focuses on the establishment of a central, user-friendly project website that will serve as the primary hub for stakeholders and the public, providing easy access to key project developments, results, and public deliverables. In addition, the chapter highlights the project's efforts to build a strategic social media presence to engage with key stakeholders, including environmental NGOs, rural development networks, journalists, and policymakers across the EU. Through platforms like LinkedIn, PHAntastic aims to foster dialogue, share updates, and expand its visibility. The chapter also details how partners will contribute to the dissemination process, ensuring that communication efforts are aligned and impactful. Targeted D&C materials such as leaflets, videos, and infographics will enhance engagement and promote the project's objectives.

Project website & blog

The project website will function as the primary resource hub, and an interactive platform for all stakeholders and the public to access project developments and results including all public deliverables and D&C outputs including leaflets, posters, presentations, latest news, videos, newsletters and will serve as a platform for advertising events such as workshops and seminars. Traffic to the website will be monitored via Google Analytics digital dashboard.

The objective of the blog is to present "quality sectoral content" (the "why") to a wide audience. It can address a range of topics linked to bio-based fertilisers and plant protection products, circular economy, recovery technologies, or even answer recurrent questions that will come up over the course of the project. Blogs, known for a more informal communicational style, have been effective in attracting audience attention, especially when accompanied by visual, audio, or video aides. With sufficient notice, the possibility to develop supportive communication material to accompany a blog can be explored and implemented. To achieve the project's goal of publishing 30 blog posts over 40 months, partners will be requested to submit two entries, aligned with their work and expertise. The estimated release date of the website is early April 2025.

Social media

PHAntastic will establish a diverse and strategic social media presence to effectively engage with key stakeholders across the EU and beyond. This includes the YouTube and LinkedIn. A list of target audiences including the key messages are displayed in

the Key stakeholders and targets of dissemination section. Our digital communication efforts will enable the project to connect with environmental NGOs, rural development networks, journalists, and EU/national-funded research initiatives, ensuring high visibility and impact.

To facilitate engagement, a dedicated LinkedIn profile has been created to interact with stakeholders, share updates, and foster dialogue. Additionally, we are exploring the establishment of a BlueSky account in collaboration with appointed technical partners to enable meaningful exchanges with the scientific community.

REVOLVE (WP7 leader) has decided to prioritize alternative social media platforms over Twitter (now X) due to multiple challenges that make it less suitable for professional and research-driven engagement. The platform has faced growing concerns over content moderation, with increasing instances of cyberbullying, misinformation, and unregulated hate speech driving many stakeholders away. Additionally, algorithm changes now favour sensational and polarizing content over informative, research-based discussions, reducing the quality of engagement for projects like PHAntastic.

Further compounding these issues is Twitter's declining credibility as a reliable source for scientific and policy-related discourse, exacerbated by the spread of misinformation. The platform's overall effectiveness has also diminished, with decreasing user engagement, lower referral traffic, and reduced return on investment (ROI) for professional content. Moreover, paid analytics requirements add unnecessary costs to performance tracking, making it less efficient for targeted communication and outreach.

In contrast, LinkedIn presents a more suitable and strategic platform for PHAntastic's communication goals. It offers direct access to key stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, industry experts, and media professionals, ensuring that project content reaches the right audience. Higher engagement rates on LinkedIn demonstrate that professional and research-based content performs better in an environment designed for knowledge sharing and networking. The platform's diverse communication tools, such as articles, videos, and discussion features, facilitate deeper engagement and long-term relationship-building.

As part of PHAntastic's strategic outreach and audience retention efforts, we are considering introducing the project on FER-PLAY's LinkedIn page, a soil-related project that is ending in February 2025 that worked on identifying circular fertiliser value chains in Europe. This would allow us to engage FER-PLAY's 980 followers and encourage them to follow PHAntastic as well. This approach would ensure that the engaged audience from the previous initiative—comprising researchers, policymakers, industry experts, and sustainability advocates in soil research—is not lost but instead transitioned into PHAntastic's network. By integrating relevant content, resources, and stakeholder interactions from the former project, we can maintain continuity in knowledge-sharing, leverage established visibility, and further strengthen engagement on crucial topics related to sustainable soil health and bio-based solutions. This merger would also help streamline communication efforts, enhance the impact of both initiatives, and maximize the reach of scientific advancements in more sustainable agricultural solutions.

To further amplify the project's reach, PHAntastic partners will actively mobilize their own communication channels, including websites and social media, to reinforce project messaging. Partners will align with the master messaging outlined in the Dissemination & Communication (D&C) plan, leveraging pre-approved online shareables and consulting with their

organizational press offices to ensure content is impactful, audience-specific, and aligned with the project's strategic objectives.

Newsletter

All press releases and newsletters under WP7 will be strategically managed to keep partners and key stakeholders well-informed. Updates will be shared exclusively with those who have provided consent through voluntary sign-ups, ensuring full compliance with EU GDPR regulations via a dedicated HubSpot account.

The PHAntastic biannual newsletter will serve as a communication tool, offering insights into project progress, preliminary findings, and upcoming internal and external events. Frequent *News Flash* updates, webinar invitations, event announcements, and publication highlights will be distributed in a LinkedIn's newsletter, ensuring timely and relevant communication to showcase the latest blog posts and resources, providing valuable insights to both new and existing followers while strengthening engagement on the platform.

Dissemination actions

All PHAntastic partners will actively contribute to dissemination efforts, ensuring that project findings and innovations reach relevant stakeholders effectively. RVL will lead and coordinate these activities, working closely with partners responsible for specific tasks to maximize outreach and impact. Dissemination efforts will include targeted communication strategies (recommendations), stakeholder engagement initiatives (events participation), and communication tools (recommendations, publications in scientific and non-scientific journals) to promote bio-based fertilisers and plant protection products across various sectors. Each partner will leverage their networks and expertise to amplify the project's visibility and ensure long-term knowledge transfer.

Policy recommendations

Towards the final phase of the four-year PHAntastic project, we will develop three targeted sets of policy recommendations aimed at accelerating the market shift towards bio-based materials and sustainable alternatives to conventional agrochemicals. These recommendations will be designed for **horticultural producers and tree nurseries (end-users of the developed product)**, **polymer producers**, and **public authorities**, ensuring that each stakeholder group receives actionable guidance relevant to their role in the transition. The process will involve stakeholder consultations, such as the 2 roundtables with EU policy makers and regulatory agencies and pilot case studies conducted throughout the project.

By synthesizing findings from real-world applications, policy frameworks, and technological advancements, PHAntastic will provide clear, evidence-based recommendations to support adoption. These will include best practices for integrating bio-based inputs in agriculture, strategies for polymer producers to scale up sustainable material production, and policy proposals

for public authorities to create an enabling regulatory and financial environment. The recommendations will be disseminated through reports, workshops (at least 4), and direct engagement with key industry players, ensuring their practical implementation and long-term impact.

Publications in sectorial magazines

As part of the communication strategy for this project, REVOLVE will engage journalists and ensure media coverage of the project throughout its course via social media content, news and press releases. We are planning to develop 4 press releases to be disseminated via HubSpot where a **database of media outlets and journalists will be gathered that is relevant to the topic of the project**. A media corner will be available on PHAntastic website providing media-friendly resources including press releases and photos for external publications. An initial list of media outlets has been set up, an excerpt of which can be found in Annex D- Excerpt from preliminary list of media outlets. Interactions with these outlets when project results will address both the professionals within the agricultural sector, but also the broader public, business and entrepreneurs, including the Brussels-based as well as international news outlets. We expect at least 40 media mentions in non-scientific articles to be published in magazines and journals throughout the project.

Scientific publications

PHAntastic will submit at least 10 scientific articles in the disciplines of agrochemicals, delivery systems, agricultural plastics and circular economy. Journals will be targeted in the D&C excel planning given scientific relevance and excellence (judged by impact factor) and open access. A list of journals frequently targeted by the consortium partners with high impact factors (this varies by discipline, with a range of c. 2.5-10.5) and open-access options will be gathered from the partners during the early phase of the project. The initial list includes journals such as Progress in Polymer Science, Accounts of Materials Research, Acta Materialia. The scientific publications will be also hosted on the PHAntastic website and cross-posted via pre-print platforms (e.g., chemRxiv, bioRxiv), and on the Open Research Europe platform once they are published.

Events participation

Consortium partners are expected to participate in 50 events to boost the outreach and increase the visibility of the results. Relevant stakeholder groups will be exposed to key messages of the project through in-person and online events. Partners will continue to refer to the outcomes of PHAntastic beyond the lifetime of the project, whenever they are invited as speakers at a relevant conference. An initial list of conferences and relevant national and international events includes PHA World Congress, European Bioplastics Conference, Ecomondo, European Organic Congress, Plast 2026. In Year 1, a preliminary list of events to attend will be collected from all partners to identify potential collaboration and opportunities to hold common events with relevant initiatives, such as sister projects, clusters etc.

Workshops

PHAntastic will organize workshops focused on engaging primarily end-users of the developed bio-based products (mulch films and growth foam), including end-users of fertilizers, pesticides, and agricultural plastics, and biopolymer manufacturers. These sessions will showcase key project activities and results while assessing social awareness and acceptance of bio-based solutions. Through live demonstrations, stakeholder discussions, and structured feedback sessions, participants will gain hands-on insights into the benefits and practical applications of sustainable alternatives to conventional agrochemicals. The workshops will also help identify market readiness, potential adoption barriers, and further refinement needs, ensuring that PHAntastic's final recommendations align with real-world demands and facilitate a smooth transition to bio-based fertilisers and plant protection products.

Synergies with relevant projects, platforms and networks

To maximize the impact of the PHAntastic project, REVOLVE will actively identify and engage with relevant initiatives, projects, and platforms at both the European and international levels. Emphasis will be placed on collaborations with beneficiaries of HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-34, which focuses on advanced nano- and bio-based materials for sustainable agriculture, fostering synergies in promoting innovative bio-based agrochemical solutions.

Table 2. Sister projects of the PHAntastic project.

Name	Duration
VINNY- Advanced nano encapsulation of bio-based pesticides and fertilisers for a circular and sustainable viticulture	June 2024-May 2028
BioBIVE- BIOdegradable delivery systems for plant pathogens control of horticultural crops through Bio-actiVE agents	June 2024-May 2028
AGRO4AGRI - FOSTERING THE ADVANCED USE OF AGROCHEMICALS FOR A SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE	May 2024-April 2028

In support of these efforts, the project will establish connections with key organizations driving sustainability and bio-based industries in Europe. These include:

- **Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU)** – A €2 billion public-private partnership dedicated to advancing Europe’s circular bio-based economy.
- **Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC)** – The private sector representative of CBE JU, striving to position Europe as a leader in bio-based innovation.
- **European Chemical Industry Council (Cefic)** – A prominent stakeholder in the chemical industry, advocating for sustainable and bio-based solutions.

Additionally, engagement with key platforms such as the **EU Nanosafety Cluster**, **European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment (EPLCA)**, and **EJP Soil** will further reinforce knowledge exchange and cross-sector collaboration.

Policy Advocacy - Project Actions to Influence Policy Discussions

As part of the project's dissemination and communication strategy, policy advocacy will play a crucial role in ensuring that research findings contribute to shaping relevant policy frameworks at the EU level. To achieve this, the consortium will develop and disseminate four targeted policy briefs addressing key areas of sustainability and bio-based innovation. These policy briefs will cover the following topics:

1. **Production of biopolymers from agricultural residues** – Supporting the **Circular Economy Action Plan** by demonstrating how agricultural waste can be transformed into valuable biopolymers, reducing reliance on fossil-based materials.
2. **Alternatives to conventional agrochemicals** – Aligning with the **Farm to Fork Strategy** and the **Zero Pollution Action Plan** by exploring bio-based solutions that can replace traditional agrochemicals, reducing soil and water contamination.
3. **Manufacture of sustainable bio-based agricultural plastics** – Contributing to the **European Industrial Strategy** by highlighting the feasibility and benefits of producing agricultural plastics using renewable bio-based resources.
4. **Incentives for bio-based and biodegradable plastics with tailored end-of-life solutions** – Advocating for policy mechanisms, in line with the **Materials 2030 Roadmap**, that encourage the adoption of biodegradable plastics and promote their effective end-of-life management.

These policy briefs will be distributed at the EU level through the networks of partners, ensuring that policymakers, industry stakeholders, and relevant regulatory bodies have access to evidence-based recommendations derived from the project’s research. For an example of a roadmap of policy advocacy, see Figure 4.

Furthermore, the consortium will actively engage in policy dialogue by participating in Public Consultations launched by the European Commission that are relevant to the project’s scope. In case such opportunities arise, REVOLVE in collaboration with ARCHA and relevant partners will aim to submit their opinion on relevant regulatory developments.

Figure 4. Roadmap to policy advocacy - an example.

To enhance outreach and stakeholder engagement, the project also aims to organise 2 roundtables with EU policymakers and regulatory agencies as well as a policy conference, fostering discussions on regulatory challenges, market opportunities, and future policy directions in the field of sustainable bio-based materials.

5. KPIs/Monitoring of dissemination and communication activities

Table 3. Communication actions that PHAntastic will implement. KPI Table.

Action	KPI	Measurement tool
Project website & blog – an easily accessible website will be created and continuously updated (in ENG)	5000 unique visits / 30 posts	Google Analytics & Matomo
Social media – a dedicated LinkedIn page will be created for interactions with stakeholders and sharing content. Partners will be encouraged to use their own social media profiles to reinforce PHAntastic communication.	1000 total followers	LinkedIn analytics
D&C materials – explaining the problem and the solution in an attractive and understandable manner, translated as necessary by partners for local use.	Audio-visual materials = 15 (5 infographics, 5 leaflets, 1 poster, 1 roll-up, 3 videos)	NA
Media – curating key messages to build credibility and visibility for the project and its results among the public to engage the interest of relevant media in the project.	4 press releases 40 media mentions	Meltwater (open and click rates)

Table 4. Dissemination actions that PHAntastic will implement. KPI table.

Action	No of target audience	KPI
Policy recommendations (e.g., for horticultural producers and tree nurseries, polymer producers and public authorities) to propel the shift of the markets towards bio-based materials and sustainable alternatives to conventional agrochemicals	1-5	3
Minimum number of events attended (trade fairs -e.g., Fruit Attraction-, conferences – e.g., PHA World Congress, European Bioplastics Conference, Ecomondo, European Organic Congress, Plast 2026-, networking events)	1-5	50
Open Access publications in scientific journals (ensuring Open Access, following FAIR data and taking advantage of EOSC)	1-6	10
Workshops to disseminate the activities and results of the project, and evaluate the social awareness and acceptance of bio-based solutions	1-6	4 workshops, 80 attendees
Roundtables with EU policy makers and regulatory agencies	4	2 roundtables, 30 experts
Policy conference	4	20 participants
Final event	1-6	150 participants
Press releases	7	4
Media mentions	7	40

6. Procedures and privacy policy

Procedures for communication

Article 17 of the Grant Agreement outlines the obligations on communications. Any promotion or communication material of PHAntastic is to include the following emblem and disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 5. EU Funding acknowledgement.

PHAntastic communications are structured by each partner identifying a core communication contact for all queries pertaining to communications. This will ensure that REVOLVE is effective in addressing questions related to specific work within the consortium or identifying problems in terms of communication.

Each contact person is responsible for answering questions on communication issues, and for reviewing, commenting on, validating, and approving the communication material produced within the framework of the project. In addition, the contact person is also responsible for ensuring the internal validation of the content/material by its respective organisation and contacting the relevant internal technical/scientific team if need be.

The activities of WP7 will be discussed with partners on an on-going basis, to provide up-to-date information and ensure the access for all partners to project materials, and that messaging is coherent and consistent.

To achieve this, a regular communication call will be deployed with a designated communication ambassador to represent each project partner. These regular update calls will allow an opportunity to align efforts of communication, resolve questions or uncertainties regarding the communication of specific project work or results, and will improve the overall lines of communication and project management and create trust and transparency amongst all partners while identifying where additional communication support will needed - i.e. for developing graphics, visuals, or additional communication materials that could support partners in their work.

Procedures for dissemination

Article 17 of the Grant Agreement outlines the procedures for Dissemination.

According to Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, each beneficiary of the project is obliged to disseminate the results that it has ownership of, in a publicly available format. Dissemination activities will remain compatible with the protection of intellectual property rights, confidentiality obligations and the legitimate interests of the owners of the results.

PHAntastic will adhere to established Open Science principles to enhance the visibility and transparency of its results, creating an innovation ecosystem that avoid duplicities and maximize the EU effort. The project's Open Science Manager (OSM), Nina Jeliaskova from IDEA, will oversee compliance with these practices. In collaboration with the relevant Work Package leaders and the exploitation leader, RTDS, the OSM will identify data and information that can be openly shared while safeguarding opportunities for commercial exploitation. Ensuring the secure management of valuable and sensitive research data will be a top priority throughout the project. Additionally, efforts will focus on addressing market entry and regulatory challenges essential for the project's successful commercialisation.

As enabled by Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement under Specific rules on Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility, the PHAntastic consortium partners have established the following procedure for Dissemination activities. The points below are paraphrased, and the Grant and Consortium Agreements remain the binding versions.

1. At least 15 calendar days' notice for any planned dissemination will be given to the coordinator and the members of the Communications Team from the other beneficiaries involved in generating the results to be presented. Notice must include sufficient information concerning the planned dissemination activity and data envisaged to be disseminated.
2. If no objections are received from the coordinator or the involved parties within this range, then the activity is permitted.
3. Any objection to the dissemination activity must be made in writing (email) to the coordinator and involved parties within 15 days of receipt of notification. An objection must include a precise request for necessary modifications. Objections are justified if:
 - A party's legitimate academic interests are compromised by the activity.
 - The activity reveals the objecting partner's intellectual property or results.
 - If an objection is received, then the involved parties will discuss how to overcome the difficulty, with FNR as arbitrator. As a guide, no partner should publish intellectual property or research results of another partner, without prior notification and written consent.
4. Once an activity has been decided upon, information about the activity must be communicated to REVOLVE, for inclusion in dissemination reporting.

7. Conclusions

This document serves an important role in supporting the PHAntastic project by establishing a structured and strategic approach to communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement. By defining key objectives, target audiences, and performance indicators, the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C Plan) ensures that the project's findings, impacts, and innovations reach the relevant stakeholders effectively and in a timely manner.

The outcomes of this document contribute directly to the project's objectives and milestones in the following ways:

1. **Enhancing Visibility and Awareness** – By identifying key stakeholders and tailoring communication strategies for different groups, the document enables meaningful interactions, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange across the agrifood sector, academia, regulatory bodies, and civil society. This maximizes public awareness and visibility, aligning with WP7's objectives.
2. **Supporting Project Impact and Synergies** – The structured dissemination strategy aligns with the project's mission to reduce agrochemical and microplastic pollution, reinforcing its contributions to EU sustainability targets such as the Farm to Fork strategy, Zero Pollution Action Plan, and the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe.' It also promotes synergies with other initiatives, amplifying the project's broader impact.
3. **Ensuring Effective Knowledge Transfer** – Through defined communication channels, materials, and strategies, the plan facilitates the flow of both internal and external communication.
4. **Monitoring and Continuous Improvement** – The inclusion of KPIs and monitoring mechanisms ensures that dissemination efforts are tracked and optimized over time, enabling iterative improvements to maximize outreach and effectiveness.

By actively involving all PHAntastic partners in dissemination efforts and integrating findings from various work packages, this document ensures that the project's innovations—PHA-based biodegradable delivery systems—gain the recognition, adoption, and policy support necessary to during the project's duration.

References

AGRO4AGRI (2025) *AGRO4AGRI: Advancing sustainable agriculture*. Available at: <https://www.agro4agri.eu> (Accessed: 5 February 2025).

BioBIVE (2025) *BioBIVE: Bio-based innovations for a vibrant economy*. Available at: <https://www.biobive.eu> (Accessed: 12 February 2025).

Bio-based Industries Consortium (2025) *BIC: Driving the bioeconomy forward*. Available at: <https://www.bbi-europe.eu> (Accessed: 8 February 2025).

CBE JU (2025) *Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU)*. Available at: <https://www.cbe.europa.eu> (Accessed: 17 February 2025).

European Joint Programme Soil (2025) *EJP Soil: Sustainable soil management for Europe*. Available at: <https://www.ejpsoil.eu> (Accessed: 22 February 2025).

EU Nanosafety Cluster (2025) *Ensuring safe innovation in nanotechnology*. Available at: <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu> (Accessed: 3 February 2025).

European Chemical Industry Council (2025) *Cefic: Representing Europe's chemical industry*. Available at: <https://www.cefic.org> (Accessed: 28 February 2025).

European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment (2025) *EPLCA: Advancing life cycle thinking*. Available at: <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu> (Accessed: 14 February 2025).

VINNY (2025) *VINNY: Valorisation of innovative bio-based products*. Available at: <https://www.vinnyproject.eu> (Accessed: 26 February 2025).

Annexes

Annex A- Visual guidelines

Introduction

The PHAntastic visual identity plays an essential role in promoting the project; as such, it is imperative to respect these guidelines when using the logo, font and colours for any external or internal communication, such as presentation templates, posters, business cards, flyers, social media, and so on.

The following guidelines provide a framework for using the brand identity in a consistent manner. Consistency communicates reliability and provides the foundation for working together in an efficient way. While maintaining the highest quality standard, our choice of words and images are opportunities to show that we understand and engage with our audiences.

These visual identity guidelines are a living document and may be updated to accommodate changing requirements. If you require assistance, additional support materials, or adjustments for a specific situation, please contact the PHAntastic team. Likewise, if for any reason, you need to work outside the scope of these visual identity guidelines, please contact the Communication leads.

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The logo / Minimum sizes & safe area	6
Colours	7
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Typography / Main typeface	9
Typography / Secondary typeface.....	10
Additional branding	11
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The logo

About the logo and its meaning

Rationale

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams.

The logo prominently features the letters "PHA" in the wordmark, designed to echo the hexagonal structures commonly found in chemical representations. This design choice serves to emphasize the project's core focus on PHA polymers and their potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

The color palette selected for the project features vibrant and engaging hues, intentionally chosen to evoke a sense of innovation, optimism, and progress. It also includes some more muted dark green and brown hues for a more natural and earthy look.

The color palette includes vibrant hues, evoking a sense of innovation and progress. The chosen typeface, Dita, is a rounded sans serif that blends the freshness of display type with the discipline of a text face, giving the branding a contemporary and approachable feel.

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The logo

Logo colour variations

Fullcolour

This is the default version of the logo, to be used on white or light backgrounds.

Dark purple + White

For use on lighter coloured backgrounds and photographs. Be careful that the logo needs to stand out against the background.

Purple + White

For use on darker coloured backgrounds and photographs. Be careful that the logo needs to stand out against the background.

Dark purple

For use on monochrome layouts or documents, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

Purple

For use on monochrome layouts or documents, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

Black

For use on black an white layouts or documents, on dark backgrounds, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

White

For use on monochrome layouts or documents, on dark backgrounds, or when the colour versions of the logo do not sufficiently stand out against the background.

PHAntastic
Visual Identity Guidelines

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The logo

Minimum size and safe area

Minimum sizes

The minimum size is indicated by the width of the logo. The logo should never be smaller than the minimum indicated sizes to avoid compromising its visibility.

The width of the inline logo should never be smaller than 25 mm in print or 70 px in digital media.

PHAntastic
Visual Identity Guidelines

Safe area

Keep all other graphic elements, logos or margins at a minimum distance as defined by the "Safe area" line. The minimum safe area is equal to the cap-height of the logo text.

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Colours

The project has an extended colour palette to meet all communication needs

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Messages

Tagline and golden paragraph to describe the project

Tagline

PHA-based innovative agricultural solutions to deliver bio-based fertilizers and plant protection products

Short tagline

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

PHAntastic
Visual Identity Guidelines

Golden paragraph

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams. Through demonstrations on horticultural crops and trees in Northern and Southern Europe, these proposed solutions, containing active bioproducts such as amino acids and microelements, have the potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

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Typography

The typeface used for PHAntastic communications is Dita

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

PHA-based innovative agricultural solutions to deliver bio-based fertilizers and plant protection products

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams. Through demonstrations on horticultural crops and trees in Northern and Southern Europe, these proposed solutions, containing active bioproducts such as amino acids and microelements, have the potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

Dita Medium

Dita Bold

Dita Regular
Minimum font size for body text: 9pt

PHAntastic
Visual Identity Guidelines

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Typography

When the recommended typeface is not available, PHAntastic communications are to use the system font Calibri

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

PHA-based innovative agricultural solutions to deliver bio-based fertilizers and plant protection products

The PHAntastic project is facilitating the sustainable transition of the agricultural sector by addressing the environmental impacts of agrochemicals and plastic pollution. By developing delivery systems based on PHAs, a type of bio-based, biodegradable polymers, the project replaces non-biodegradable plastics and synthetic agrochemicals with eco-friendly mulch films and growth foams. Through demonstrations on horticultural crops and trees in Northern and Southern Europe, these proposed solutions, containing active bioproducts such as amino acids and microelements, have the potential to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, while decreasing microplastic pollution and promoting soil health.

Calibri Bold

Calibri Regular
Minimum font size for body text: 9pt

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Additional branding

Other logos and mentions to include in PHAntastic communications

As a Horizon Europe funded project, PHAntastic communication activities and products must also include the EU flag and following disclaimer:

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Contact

For any questions regarding these guidelines, please contact the communication partner:

Contact person

Dorottya Kalo
Communication Coordinator, REVOLVE
dorottya@revolve.media

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Follow our project
phantastic-project.eu

P.H. Antastic

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**Annex B-
Templates
(PowerPoint,
Word,Press
Release)**

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title**

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Not yet approved by the EC.

 P.H. Antastic

 P.H. Antastic

1

Fusce dapibus, tellus
ac cursus commodo,
tortor mauris
condimentum nibh, ut
fermentum massa
justo sit amet risus.

2

Fusce dapibus, tellus
ac cursus commodo,
tortor mauris
condimentum nibh, ut
fermentum massa
justo sit amet risus.

3

Fusce dapibus, tellus
ac cursus commodo,
tortor mauris
condimentum nibh, ut
fermentum massa
justo sit amet risus.

4

Fusce dapibus, tellus
ac cursus commodo,
tortor mauris
condimentum nibh, ut
fermentum massa
justo sit amet risus.

Jonathan Doe

Integer posuere erat a ante
venenatis dapibus posuere
velit aliquet.

Jonathan Doe

Integer posuere erat a ante
venenatis dapibus posuere
velit aliquet.

Jonathan Doe

Integer posuere erat a ante
venenatis dapibus posuere
velit aliquet.

Jonathan Doe

Integer posuere erat a ante
venenatis dapibus posuere
velit aliquet.

Title 1

Fusce dapibus, tellus ac cursus commodo, tortor mauris condimentum nibh, ut fermentum massa justo sit amet risus.

Title 2

Fusce dapibus, tellus ac cursus commodo, tortor mauris condimentum nibh, ut fermentum massa justo sit amet risus.

Title 3

Fusce dapibus, tellus ac cursus commodo, tortor mauris condimentum nibh, ut fermentum massa justo sit amet risus.

Title 4

Fusce dapibus, tellus ac cursus commodo, tortor mauris condimentum nibh, ut fermentum massa justo sit amet risus.

Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod semper. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Nulla vitae elit libero, a pharetra augue. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus.

Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod semper. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Nulla vitae elit libero, a pharetra augue. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus.

Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod semper. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Nulla vitae elit libero, a pharetra augue. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus.

Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod semper. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Nulla vitae elit libero, a pharetra augue. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus.

Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod semper. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Nulla vitae elit libero, a pharetra augue. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus.

Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod semper. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Nulla vitae elit libero, a pharetra augue. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus.

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 P.H. Antastic

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Subtitle

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DX.X. DELIVERABLE TITLE

Deliverable Information Sheet

Version	
Grant Agreement Number	
Project Acronym	
Project Title	
Project Call	
Project Duration	
Deliverable Number	
Deliverable Title	
Deliverable Type	
Deliverable Dissemination Level ¹	
Work Package	
Lead Partner	
Authors	
Contributing Partners	
Reviewers	
Official Due Date	
Delivery Date	

Revisions

Version	Date	Comments	Authors

¹ Type [1] R=Document, report; DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; DEC=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER=other_
Dissemination level [1] PU=Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CI=Classified

DX.X. DELIVERABLE TITLE

Document verification and approval

	Name	Organisation	Date	Visa
Internal Review				
WP Leader				
PHAntastic manager				
Project Coordinator				

List of Acronyms

DX.X. DELIVERABLE TITLE

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Keywords list

- Ultricies
- Sit Inceptos
- Pellentesque
- Lorem

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Not yet approved by the EC.

1. Executive summary

1.1. Heading 2

Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna. Donec sed odio dui.

“Quote: Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Cum sociis natoque penatibus et magnis dis parturient montes, nascetur ridiculus mus.

– Author

1.1.1. Heading 3

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Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Praesent commodo cursus magna, vel scelerisque nisl consectetur et. Donec sed odio dui. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros.

DX.X. DELIVERABLE TITLE

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1.1.1.1. Heading 4

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Dkjkkljkljkl				
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Table 1. Table Example

Figure 1. Solutions

Donec sed odio dui. Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Donec sed odio dui. Praesent commodo cursus magna, vel scelerisque nisl consectetur et. Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros.

2. Introduction

Not yet approved by the EC.

3. Xxxxxxx

Not yet approved by the EC.

4. Conclusions

Not yet approved by the EC.

5. References

Not yet approved by the EC.

6. Annex

Not yet approved by the EC.

Not yet approved by the EC.

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Not yet approved by the EC.

Heading 1

1.1. Heading 2

Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna. Donec sed odio dui.

“Quote: Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Cum sociis natoque penatibus et magnis dis parturient montes, nascetur ridiculus mus.

– Author

1.1.1. Heading 3

Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna. Donec sed odio dui.

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- Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna.

Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Praesent commodo cursus magna, vel scelerisque nisl consectetur et. Donec sed odio dui. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros.

Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Praesent commodo cursus magna, vel scelerisque nisl consectetur et. Donec sed odio dui. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros.

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1.1.1.1. Heading 4

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Dkjkljkljkljkl				
efhgjgh				

Table 1. Table Example

Figure 1. Solutions

Donec sed odio dui. Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Donec sed odio dui. Praesent commodo cursus magna, vel scelerisque nisl consectetur et. Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros.

CONTACT DETAILS
Dorottya Kalo, Communication Coordinator
dorottya@revolve.media

PRESS RELEASE

DATE
01/11/2024

Heading 1

Heading 2

Heading 3

Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna. Donec sed odio dui.

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– Author

Morbi leo risus, porta ac consectetur ac, vestibulum at eros. Cras justo odio, dapibus ac facilisis in, egestas eget quam. Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet non magna. Donec sed odio dui.

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CONTACT DETAILS

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PRESS RELEASE

DATE

01/11/2024

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*** ENDS ***

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[boilerplate] About PROJECT NAME

[call to action] Want to know more about EU projects on sustainability? Or speak to a sustainability expert on topics such as energy transition or sustainable cities? Then join REVOLVE's pool of journalists here.

Media contact

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mobile:

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Annex C- Project Roll up

P.H.Antastic

Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

The PHAntastic project uses polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) to develop biodegradable mulch film and growth foam delivery systems, reducing the need for synthetic agrochemical inputs and non-biodegradable polymers.

Follow our project
<https://phantastic-project.eu/>

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Annex D- Excerpt from preliminary list of media outlets

Country of interest	Name of outlets
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agroinformación - Revista Tierras - Agrodigital - iAgua - Ecoticias - El País - La Vanguardia - Agronews Castilla y León - La Voz del Campo - Revista Agricultura - COAG - Agropopular (Cadena COPE) - Mediterráneo Radio 3 - Vida Verde Radio 4
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agronotizie - L'Informatore Agrario - Terra e Vita - Coldiretti - Il Sole 24 Ore (Agriculture Section) - Corriere della Sera (Agriculture Section) - Confagricoltura - Legambiente - Radio Rai 1 - Radio 24
The Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boerderij - De Volkskrant (Agriculture Section) - Groentennieuws - Nieuwe Oogst - Friesch Dagblad - Limburgs Dagblad - LTO Nederland - Radio 1 (Agri Business)
Austria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Die Landwirtschaft (Agriculture Magazine) - BauernZeitung - Bio Austria - Top Agrar Austria - Der Standard (Agriculture Section) - Kurier - ORF Radio 1
Belgium (Flemish speaking)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boerenbond - VILT (Vlaams Instituut voor Landbouw- en

	Visserijonderzoek) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Landbouwleven - De Standaard (Agriculture Section) - Het Laatste Nieuws (Agriculture Section) - Zondag - Radio 2 (Flemish)
EU level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EURACTIV - POLITICO Europe - EU Observer - REVOLVE

Not yet approved by the EC.